

Area-specific vocalisation and activity monitoring in pigs

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Abstract

Vocalisations and activity are important factors for monitoring animal behaviour. Previous studies have shown that these parameters are altered in the context of disease, farrowing and distress. In the highly standardized conditions of livestock farming, these contexts are often closely linked to specific areas of the barn – allowing information about specific animal states to be inferred from these rather unspecific parameters. We have developed a sensor that uses acoustic beamforming and radar to measure vocalisations and activity in defined areas. The sensor was tested in two settings. Firstly, recently weaned piglets were socially isolated with unrestricted sensory contact for up to 20 minutes. During this comparatively mild distress, stress vocalisations could be detected with 63 % sensitivity, 97 % specificity, and 79 % balanced normalized precision. Secondly, data recorded in the context of farrowing demonstrated that the sensor is able to distinguish between movement and vocalisation events in adjacent pens. To quantify the sensor's spatial differentiation, we compared an empty and an adjacent occupied farrowing pen over the time of birth, using Receiver Operating Characteristics curve (ROC). The ROC curves for discriminating the activity in the pens reached an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.87 to 0.95, whereby 0.5 would be the worst and 1.0 the best performance. The ROC curves for discriminating sources of stress events reached an AUC of 0.86 to 0.96. Furthermore, this technology is currently being adapted for applications in other farm animal species.

Keywords: area-specific vocalisation analysis, radar activity, beamforming, farm animal behaviour

Introduction

New sensor technology and data evaluation techniques enable continuous monitoring of farm animal behaviour. This development bears the potential for automated quality control and more efficient work organisation in livestock farming. Livestock farming is organised around the repeating live cycle of the animals in terms of growing, mating and breeding. Specific sections of this cycle are bound to specific areas in the barn. Thus, monitoring equipment installed in these areas can incorporate the biological processes as context information in the interpretation of the recorded data. This entails two benefits: First, installing sensors in the barn instead of attaching them to the animals can be more cost-effective in terms of workload and number of sensor units needed. Secondly, incorporating the biological contexts can allow for the use of relatively simple and general parameters to monitor specific behaviour.

The present study investigated whether the parameters “general movement activity” and “vocalisation events” are suited in this regard. The data was recorded using a novel sensor device that combined radar based movement detection and a microphone array for bioacoustics and beamforming. These measurement systems are supposed to be especially suited for the use in farms as they are robust with regard to the adverse environmental conditions such as variable lighting, insects, dust, and corrosive air. At the same time, there are well-established scientific findings regarding which changes in activity and vocalisations occur in which biological contexts. In pigs, altered movement activity is, for example, linked to illness (Weary et al., 2009), tail biting (Zonderland et al., 2011) and farrowing (Lammers and De Lange, 1986). Besides, pigs vocalise a lot to provide information to their fellow animals. In particular, pigs express anxiety, pain and other types of distress through stress vocalisations. This specific type of vocalisation can be detected automatically using the so called stress monitoring and documentation (STREMODO) system (Schön et al., 2001, 2004).

The underlying algorithm of STREMODO was originally implemented in the LabVIEW programming language. It was recently re-implemented in C++ by the authors to allow its use in a compact sensor. Therefore, the re-implementation required the exchange of the underlying utility libraries for LPC calculation and the neuronal network. One aim of the present study was to evaluate whether these changes led to a different detection performance. For this purpose, we evaluated stress vocalisation data from an independent trial where piglets were handled and isolated (Moscovice et al., 2023). In addition, it was evaluated how well the sensor can discriminate between signals from different pens in an experimental setup where a sensor above an empty pen served as reference. Here, the number of events detected in the empty pen gave an impression of how well signals from neighbouring pens were rejected by the sensor. This kind of spatial filtering forms a precondition for most practical use cases. It was investigated here as a proof of concept in the context of a project on the automated behaviour detection in dairy goats. We present data for the pen wise recording of data in the context of farrowing of sows since an installation in a goat barn was not ready at the time of the study. It was previously shown that spatially filtered sensor data can be used to forecast and detect farrowing in sows (Manteuffel, 2019) and to detect piglet crushing (Manteuffel et al., 2017).

Material and Methods

To conduct our measurements, we utilised a device that combines a radar sensor and a microphone array for beamforming, along with the STREMODO evaluation software for stress detection. The device was installed in a stable-proof (IP 67) box on a metal framework in a standardized height of 2.5 m nearly central above the pen of interest. (Fig.1B)

Figure 1: A - Overview sketch of the experimental setup in the farrowing compartment. The sensor box a), the cameras b) and the sow in the pen c) are highlighted.

B - Detailed sketch of the stable-proof sensor box with removed cover. The focussed radar module a) and the openings for the microphones of the Beamforming module b) are visible.

RADAR – radio detection and ranging

The movement activity was monitored using a 5 GHz radar module for presence detection (DFRobot SEN0192). The evaluation of the radar signal was limited to the detection of spatially expansive movements in the monitored area. The monitored area was controlled by limiting the angle of the radar-emission through radar damping material. The velocity and distance of the movement could not be analysed with this type of sensor.

Bio-acoustic measurements

Every noise event located under the sensor was detected as acoustic activity. The STREMOD0 vocalisation analysis software was used to differentiate the recorded events between stress-related vocalisation and general sounds (Schön et al., 2001). The direction of arrival was estimated using an open source beamforming library (Grondin and Michaud, 2018), and a quadratic microphone array with 4 microphones (ReSpeaker 4mic array). The microphone array was installed pointing to the floor of the stable. Thus, the elevation angle of a sound source could be utilised to limit the recordings to sound sources from the pen underneath the sensor. The recording consisted of a text protocol that contained one entry per 100 ms. Each entry entailed the date and time, the detection of stress, the volume and amplification and the estimated elevation angle of the predominant source of the sound. An additional text protocol contained the activity count and duration accumulated over a period of 10 seconds.

Experimental Setup

For determining the stress detection performance, we used data from a different trial at our facility (Moscovice et al., 2023) which wasn't analysed and published in this way before. For this study, piglets were housed in identical neighbouring pens sized 2.8 x 2.8

m. During the trial, randomly chosen piglets were moved to an adjacent experimental compartment where they were physically isolated from the group for up to 20 minutes. Sensory, i.e., acoustic, visual and olfactory contact to the group was not restricted. The handling of the piglets and the isolation induced stress vocalisation, which was retrospectively evaluated by a human observer and STREMODO. The human observers were experienced in working with pigs and marked all screams of the piglets following their professional intuition. The evaluated dataset contains the vocalisation from $n = 75$ piglets with an age between 46 and 55 days.

The measurements in the context of farrowing were taken in two trials of 4 weeks each, within the farrowing compartment of the Experimental Pig Facility Unit of the Research Institute for Farm Animal Biology (FBN) in Dummerstorf, Germany. One compartment contained six 2 x 2.5 m sized farrowing pens located directly adjacent to each other. In each of the six pens, one behaviour sensor was installed in approximately 2.5 m height above the centre of the pen (Fig. 1A). The distance between the centres of two adjacent pens was 2 m. The six pens were linearly arranged in the room. Per run, the first four pens were occupied with sows (German Landrace). Generally, the last two pens remained unoccupied. Only the first four of the six pens were equipped with cameras to monitor the animal behaviour and identify the onset of farrowing. All observations were conducted under normal husbandry conditions. In particular, no measures were taken to ensure a uniform occupation of the pens with regard to the number of piglets or the age of the sow as this was a pilot study to evaluate the performance of the sensor in the discrimination of events between the neighbouring pens. During the study, three sensors malfunctioned so that their data could not be evaluated. In the second trial, one of the sows gave birth to just one live piglet. This piglet was moved to a different pen, directly after the intake of colostrum. Therefore, the spatial discrimination between occupied and empty pens could only be evaluated with one “half occupied” (i.e., a sow but no piglets) pen between the evaluated empty and fully occupied pen.

Stress detection

The performance evaluation was done using R-Statistical Software (R Core Team, 2013). The evaluation of stress detection performance was only done for the data from the piglet isolation trial (Moscovice et al., 2023). Here, all events classified as stress by the human observers formed the set of true positive events. A set of audible events with a minimal length of 500 ms was automatically created using a threshold-based approach for the increase and decrease of the acoustic volume. These events minus the true positive events were taken as the true negative event set (acoustic events that are not stress vocalisation). Misclassifications by STREMODO were correspondingly all positive events that were not detected and all erroneously detected events from the negative event set.

Location discrimination

The location discrimination was evaluated by assuming zero stress events and zero movement activity as true positive events for the empty pens and all recorded events for the occupied pen. False positive was any event detected by the sensors above the empty pens. The events in the neighbouring pen were incorporated as the negative event class so that every event below the threshold was counted as true negative for the empty pen and false negative for the occupied pen. Based on these definitions the area under the ROC-curve (AUC) for the parameters movement activity and stress vocalisation were

calculated (Eq.1). Here, vocalisation activity was defined as event under the sensor with an angle higher than 42 degrees and a volume of at least -35 dB in the value domain of minus infinity (silent) to zero (highest detectable loudness). Only these sound sources were incorporated in the stress detection. Movement activity was recorded whenever the antenna received a sufficiently strong reflected signal with a recognisable Doppler frequency shift. The radar measurements were evaluated to quantify the effect of false readings, e.g., due to insufficient damping of the side beams and from movements of the sensor or its mounting equipment.

$$AUC = \int_0^{t_{max}} \frac{Sensitivity(t)}{1-Specificity(t)} dt \quad (1)$$

To show that the sensor readings reflect specific changes in the biological state of animals, we show two example charts for movement activity and stress vocalisation in the context of farrowing. Here, the movement activity was depicted as a transformed curve - as it would be used for farrowing prediction. Specifically, we calculated the difference between the current activity and a 3 hour average from 24 hours before (Eq.2). Without behavioural changes, this curve is centred around zero. An activity increase would shift the mean to a positive value. Successive readings of increased activity can be detected by calculating the cumulate sum of the activity differences (Eq.3).

$$t2tdiff(t) = mean(t) - mean(t - 24) \quad (2)$$

$$CUSUM(t) = \max(0, CUSUM(t - 1) + t2tdiff(t)) \quad (3)$$

Results

Stress detection

The re-implemented STREMODODO stress detection software tended to misclassify hiss sounds, e.g., from nipple drinkers and metal noises from the pen equipment. Stress vocalisations were detected with 63 % sensitivity, 97 % specificity, and 79 % balanced normalized precision in comparison to human observers and with regard to the established classification performance metrics and the newly proposed normalised precision (Manteuffel et al., 2021).

Location discrimination

In the first trial, movement activity was localised by radar with an AUC of 0.87 (Fig. 2 A, B). Stress events were discriminated with an AUC of 0.96 (Fig. 2 C, D). In the second run, movement activity was discriminated with an AUC of 0.95 (Fig. 2 E, F), whereas an AUC of 0.86 was achieved for stress detection (Fig. 2 G, H). The measurements were selected randomly and are not necessarily linked to farrowing.

Figure 2: Number of movement events and stress events under the sensor of the occupied pen (black) and an empty pen (coloured). In the first run (A-D) the pens were directly adjacent. In the second run, one pen with a single sow was located between the sensors (E-H). (n=2)
The area under the curve (AUC) is performed by integrating the sets of true positive rates (TPR/sensitivity) and true negative rates (TNR/1-Specificity) for different threshold values.

Biological context

Figure 3 shows two curves for the movement activity (cumulated sum of differences in movement activity) and stress events (raw data). The purpose is to illustrate how the sensor picks up fundamental changes in the animal behaviour in the context of farrowing (dashed line). Roughly 24 - 48 h before the onset of labour, the sows start to show increased movement activity (Lammers and De Lange, 1986). Stress vocalisation increases once the piglets are born. This has several causes, for example fights for teat access before suckling, regular treatments such as vaccinations and piglets being trapped by the sows leg or underneath other piglets. Both effects can be seen in the recorded data.

Figure 3: The upper (black) curves show the cumulated sum of 24 h activity differences measured via radar. The lower (red) curve depicts the raw number of stress events detected by the sensor. The vertical dashed line (blue) marks the birth of the first piglet in the pen. Plot A shows data from the first run while B shows a pen from the second trial-run. (n=2)

Discussion

The presented data show that the re-implemented STREMODODO system for vocalisation analysis is able to detect stress vocalisation in piglets with high specificity. Furthermore, it could be shown that our sensor system is able to discriminate movement activity and vocalisation events with a practically relevant performance even if two sensors are only 2 m apart. This means that a pen-wise recording of animal behaviour is possible. The sensitivity of the sensors with the STREMODODO algorithm appears to be sufficient to detect relevant changes in piglet behaviour like trapped piglets during nursing. The location context is very important for the interpretation because it is only valid for sows in the last days of gestation and for individually housed sows. Here, the sensor data can also be utilised to obtain information about changes in the underlying biological context. Piglet crushing is most probable within the first days of live. Since the sensor should be able to detect the farrowing, it can determine the age of the piglets and therefore it can also autonomously determine the period with high crushing probability which is then again incorporated in the interpretation of the sensor data.

If this concept can be utilised to aid in the interpretation of the sensor data within other biological contexts still needs to be evaluated. One promising candidate is tail-biting in the flat deck or fattening pen. However, it has to be further investigated whether the error rates of the stress detection and location discrimination are sufficient for these use cases. In addition, the voice characteristics of pigs change with their age. Therefore, the performance of STREMODODO should be re-evaluated in older pigs. It may be necessary to create a vocalisation analysis that is adapted to the age of the pig. The age of the pigs is another biological context that is directly linked to the location of the measurement and therefore can easily be incorporated for the interpretation of the sensor data. Furthermore, the same concept might be transferred to use cases in other species such as goats, cattle, and horses. This requires that the respective species show sufficiently expressive vocalisation behaviour. An application in goat is currently investigated in the project VerZi in the context of which the present study was performed.

Conclusion

We found first indications that area-specific monitoring systems for movement and vocalisation events are possible in pigs and can be used to infer information on practically relevant animal states by incorporating the biological context of the measurements. This still has to be confirmed with more data from contexts like farrowing, weaning, fattening or even slaughter. In the future, the vocalisation analysis may be adapted to other farm animal species such as goats.

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